

FCT RESEARCH AND INNOVATION LANDSCAPE COUNTRY PROFILE: PORTUGAL

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Overview

The **Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT)** domain is a critical pillar within the European Union's security research framework, designed to address the increasingly complex and transnational threats facing Europe today. **FCT** research aims to provide innovative solutions, tools, and knowledge to empower law enforcement, policymakers, and civil society to prevent, detect, and respond to criminal and terrorist activities across the continent. The European Union supports collaborative research and innovation through key programmes like **Horizon Europe**, focusing on multidisciplinary approaches that combine advanced technology with robust legal, ethical, and societal safeguards.

In line with **ENACT's** objectives, this flash report is part of a series of reports that reviews the **FCT R&I** ecosystem in each EU Member State based on their participation in EU-funded **Security Research** under the **FCT** area between 2021 and 2024. The data used for the report comes from the most recent data available from **CORDIS** and the **Horizon Dashboard**, combined with data processed by **ENACT** under its **Structured Knowledge Base (SKB)**.

Portugal Infobox

Capital: Lisbon

Official EU Language(s): Portuguese

EU Member State: since 1 January 1986

Currency: euro (€)

Euro Area Member: since 1 January 1999

Schengen Area Member: since 26 March 1995

Figures

- **Geographical size:** 92 226km²
- **Population:** 10 749 635 (2025)

Portugal's position as a peripheral but strategically connected Member State,¹ with extensive maritime borders and strong links to Atlantic trade routes, shapes both its participation in EU internal-security cooperation and its exposure to transnational crime dynamics. Its geographic location, including major ports and connections to Africa and Latin America, places the country along key transit routes for illicit flows, while its integration in the Schengen Area facilitates cross-border mobility.

To contextualise how these structural characteristics translate into concrete crime dynamics, analytical assessments such as the Global Organised Crime Index (OCINDEX) examine the main illicit markets, the types of actors involved and the institutional responses addressing these threats.

According to the OCINDEX,² Portugal is primarily identified as a transit country for **Drug Trafficking**, particularly cocaine, supported by maritime routes connecting Latin America, Africa and Europe. The profile also highlights **Human Trafficking** and **Migrant Smuggling, Financial and Economic Crime**, and the growing relevance of **Cyber-enabled Crime**. The organised crime landscape is characterised mainly by flexible, network-based structures, often operating in cooperation with foreign actors.

¹https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/eu-countries/portugal_en

²Global Organised Crime Index: https://ocindex.net/assets/downloads/2025/english/ocindex_profile_portugal_2025.pdf

Within this context, Portugal has established a consistent presence within the European security R&I ecosystem under **Horizon Europe Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society**. Portuguese organisations participate across a diverse range of projects addressing **Organised Crime, Cybercrime**, terrorism prevention, and societal resilience. Although the overall scale of participation remains smaller than that of larger Member States, Portugal demonstrates one of the strongest success rates in proposal evaluations and contributes specialised expertise in several key capability areas.

Portugal’s innovation system has also demonstrated steady progress in recent years. National investment in research and development increased significantly between 2020 and 2023, reaching approximately €4.5 billion, while human resources dedicated to R&D activities have also grown, particularly in fields such as engineering, digital technologies, and information sciences.³

Portuguese participation is characterised by a focused and strategic engagement, with actors often contributing in roles related to **Digital Investigations, Intelligence Analysis, Forensic Capabilities**, and **Training Activities**. The country’s research ecosystem benefits from close collaboration between law enforcement authorities, research institutes, universities, and specialised technology organisations, enabling the translation of research outcomes into operational tools and methodologies.

³ Agência Nacional de Inovação (2025) Relatório Nacional de Inovação 2024 (en: National Innovation Report 2024) Available online: https://ani.pt/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/RNI2024_06082025.pdf

Country overview in FCT Research & Innovation

Portugal's country profile in the **FCT** domain will be examined from three perspectives: policy coverage, functional coverage, and technology, in accordance with the **EU Civil Security Taxonomy (EUCST)**.⁴

FCT Policy Coverage

The figure below illustrates the policy coverage of Portuguese participation, categorised into the main **Security Research** areas: **OC (Organised Crime)**, **TR (Terrorism and Radicalisation)**, **CC (Cybercrime)**, and **HSI (Other Horizontal Societal Issues)**. Figure 2 further disaggregates this engagement by showing the distribution across the relevant policy sub-areas within each theme. This distribution is based on the participation of Portuguese entities in **FCT** topics, as well as their perceived areas of expertise identified through fairs and conferences.

Overall, Portugal's participation in the **FCT** research landscape shows a diversified thematic distribution across the policy domains defined in the **EUCST**. Portuguese involvement is most strongly represented in **CC**, followed by **HSI** and **OC**, while **TR** topics also maintain a significant presence.

Figure 1: Policy coverage across Portuguese participants in the ENACT Stakeholders Directory

⁴https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/eu-security-market-study/eu-civil-security-taxonomy-and-taxonomy-explorer_en

Within the **CC** domain, the largest share of Portuguese participation is concentrated in projects focusing on a range of issues related to technologically enabled crime. Portuguese actors are particularly active in areas addressing **Dark Net** activities and illegal online markets, as well as other forms of **Cybercrime** and **Digital Forensics**. This strong representation reflects Portugal’s growing expertise in digital investigation and cyber-enabled crime prevention.

The **HSI** domain represents the second most relevant area of Portuguese participation. Activities in this domain address a wide range of societal security challenges, including domestic violence and sexual abuse, conventional forensic practices, and disinformation and fake news, highlighting the integration of social, behavioural, and community-oriented approaches within the Portuguese security research profile.

Within the **OC** domain, Portuguese participation is primarily focused on the **Trafficking of Humans and Goods**, which is the most prominent topic. Significant activity is also observed in **Economic Crime**, corruption and fraud. This profile indicates a focus on transnational and economically driven criminal activities.

The **TR** domain is also well represented, with Portuguese contributions addressing **Radicalisation** and the **Protection of Public Spaces** as key areas. These activities reflect a focus on prevention, resilience, and the protection of public environments.

Figure 2: Policy coverage at level 3 across Portuguese stakeholders

FCT Functions Coverage

Figure 3 presents Portugal’s functional profile within the **FCT** research ecosystem, which demonstrates a strong concentration in investigative and analytical functions, supported by complementary capabilities in training, communication, and intelligence management. The distribution of functional activities reflects a profile oriented towards operational support to **Law Enforcement** and data-driven investigation.

The most prominent functional area is **Investigation and Forensics**, which represents by far the largest share of Portuguese participation. This includes activities related to both digital and conventional forensic analysis, highlighting Portugal’s strong positioning in evidence collection, processing, and analysis within criminal investigations. This dominance confirms the central role of Portuguese actors in supporting investigative workflows across multiple crime domains, particularly **Cybercrime**.

A second group of highly represented functions includes **Data, Information and Intelligence Gathering, Management and Exploitation, Training and Exercises**, and **Secure and Public Communication, Data and Information Exchange**. These areas show a consistent level of activity and reflect Portugal’s engagement in strengthening information-sharing mechanisms, capacity-building, and interoperability among security actors. The emphasis on training also indicates a contribution to enhancing operational readiness and knowledge transfer across European **Law Enforcement** communities.

Figure 3: Functions coverage across Portuguese stakeholders

FCT Technology Domain Coverage

As can be observed in Figure 4, the technological profile of Portuguese contributions is closely aligned with its functional strengths in investigation, forensics, and intelligence exploitation. Portugal’s participation in the **FCT** research ecosystem demonstrates a strong concentration in digital and data-driven technologies, which reflects its positioning in areas related to **Cybercrime** investigation, information management, and secure communications.

The most prominent technological domain is **Internet-based Investigation**, representing the largest share of Portuguese activity. This includes tools and solutions designed to support investigations in online environments, particularly in relation to **Cybercrime** and illicit digital markets. This is complemented by a strong presence in **Data Storage and Exchange** technologies, highlighting Portugal’s involvement in systems that enable secure and efficient information sharing across organisations and borders.

Portugal also demonstrates significant participation in **Critical and Interoperable Communication Systems**, reflecting efforts to enhance coordination and communication between **Law Enforcement** and security actors. Similarly, **Digital Forensics** technologies and **Data Analytics** represent key areas of engagement, supporting the processing, analysis, and interpretation of large volumes of digital evidence.

This distribution reflects a broader specialisation in cyber-enabled security technologies and intelligence-driven approaches, aligning with both national capabilities and evolving European security priorities.

Figure 4: Technology coverage across Portuguese stakeholders

Overview of Portugal's Horizon Europe participation metrics

The next figure compares Portugal's and the EU's key performance indicators in the **Horizon Europe FCT** domain, highlighting Portugal's strong engagement and specific contributions relative to the European reference figures.

Portugal	21	1.33	€ 246,312.42	€ 234,501.05	3	€ 668,756.25
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution
EU	41	18.12	€ 4,310,115.27	€ 3,987,660.71	172	€ 44,114,024.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution

Figure 5: Portuguese project participation metrics compared to the EU

In this period, 21 out of 41 signed **FCT** grants include Portuguese beneficiaries, representing a sizable portion of EU activity in this domain. Portugal is involved in a comparable number of signed projects to leading countries, positioning itself alongside them in terms of project participation, despite a smaller national research ecosystem. In terms of participation, Portugal records a more limited presence, reflecting a lower number of organisations involved in each project on average.

On average, an **FCT** grant includes 18.12 beneficiaries, of which 1.33 are Portuguese. Portuguese beneficiaries also hold, on average, 5.88% of the grants' budget, indicating a relevant level of involvement in project activities. With respect to SME participation, Portuguese SMEs represent only 1.7% of the total number of SMEs involved in **FCT** grants under the **Horizon Europe** programme.

Portugal's overall level of participation and funding within the FCT research ecosystem remains comparatively modest when viewed against larger Member States, a trend that is closely linked to the country's smaller economic and industrial scale. The relatively limited number of participating organisations, together with lower levels of SME involvement and reduced total EU contribution, reflects the structure of a more compact national innovation system. In particular, the smaller presence of SMEs, both in terms of participation and allocated funding, suggests a less extensive private-sector base engaged in security research when compared to countries such as Spain or Italy.

At the same time, Portugal demonstrates a remarkably strong level of engagement relative to its size, ranking among the most active countries in terms of signed grants and overall participation. This indicates that Portuguese organisations are able to compete effectively with larger Member States, leveraging a focused and well-coordinated research ecosystem. Despite structural limitations, Portugal's ability to secure a high number of projects highlights its competitiveness and its capacity to position itself as a relevant and reliable partner within European security research consortia.

Based on the indicators presented in Figure 5 and the country comparison data in Table 1, Portugal ranks ninth in terms of total participations.

Country Code	Country	Signed Grants	Total Participations by Country	Net EU Contribution
EL	Greece	34	90	€ 26,290,653.24
ES	Spain	34	87	€ 17,409,733.00
IT	Italy	25	65	€ 17,590,799.90
UK	United Kingdom	30	52	€ 4,525,528.75
DE	Germany	27	48	€ 13,558,133.33
FR	France	21	43	€ 10,163,819.63
BE	Belgium	23	39	€ 9,606,930.16
FI	Finland	22	29	€ 5,954,334.86
PT	Portugal	21	28	€ 4,924,522.00
NL	Netherlands	19	27	€ 8,513,248.75
PL	Poland	16	26	€ 5,898,789.00
CY	Cyprus	18	23	€ 5,723,581.25
RO	Romania	14	22	€ 2,733,978.00
MD	Moldova	18	20	€ 1,288,120.00
AT	Austria	12	16	€ 4,347,636.75
BG	Bulgaria	6	13	€ 2,241,263.14
CZ	Czechia	10	13	€ 2,061,742.25
LU	Luxembourg	10	11	€ 4,401,443.75
IE	Ireland	7	10	€ 3,456,761.80
SE	Sweden	10	10	€ 2,128,071.25
EE	Estonia	7	9	€ 1,177,348.75
SI	Slovenia	4	8	€ 1,201,050.00
IL	Israel	4	5	€ 1,761,025.00
RS	Serbia	4	5	€ 478,496.25
HU	Hungary	3	4	€ 1,731,153.75
NO	Norway	3	3	€ 1,071,048.75
SK	Slovakia	1	3	€ 831,038.50
HR	Croatia	2	3	€ 602,395.26
LT	Lithuania	2	3	€ 420,080.00
MT	Malta	3	3	€ 283,356.00
CA	Canada	2	2	€ 418,417.50
TR	Türkiye	1	2	€ 160,432.50
DK	Denmark	2	2	€ 107,375.00
XK	Kosovo *	2	2	€ 78,750.00
MK	North Macedonia	2	2	€ 67,226.25
UA	Ukraine	1	1	€ 135,000.00
BA	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1	€ 59,625.00
AL	Albania	1	1	€ 48,750.00
IS	Iceland	1	1	€ 42,430.00
CH	Switzerland	8	11	€ 0.00

Table 1: Comparison of Portugal to other participating countries in Horizon Europe for signed grants, total project participations and net EU contribution

Participants Summary

Portuguese participation in **Horizon Europe CL3-FCT** projects encompasses a broad range of organisations, including research centres, universities, industry, and public sector bodies. The involvement of both well-established institutions and emerging players signals a robust and healthy ecosystem.

Figure 6: Organisational types of Portuguese participation compared to the EU average in Horizon Europe projects

Particularly significant is the active role played by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), reflecting both scientific excellence and application-driven project designs. When analysing individual participants by their type, the following overview highlights the current key organisations involved.

Top End Users

End User	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Ministerio da Justica	€ 1,315,275.00	10	€ 1,315,274.50
MINISTERIO DA ADMINISTRACAO INTERNA	€ 322,818.75	3	€ 322,818.75
CAMARA MUNICIPAL DE LISBOA	€ 284,562.50	2	€ 284,562.50
Grand Total	€ 1,922,656	15	€ 1,922,656

Top Research and Technology Organisations

Research and Technology Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
INOV INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES INOVACAO	€ 1,190,812.50	4	€ 1,190,812.50
I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	€ 415,278.75	2	€ 415,278.75
INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIENCIA	€ 237,500.00	1	€ 237,500.00
Grand Total	€ 1,843,591	7	€ 1,843,591

Top Industry

Industrial Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
PARTICLE SUMMARY	€ 423,000.00	1	€ 296,100.00
GLOBAZ, S.A.	€ 403,794.64	1	€ 282,656.25
CIHP, CYBER INTELLIGENCE HOUSE PORTUGAL, SOCIEDADE UNIPessoal LDA	€ 191,250.00	1	€ 191,250.00
QUALIFY JUST - IT SOLUTIONS AND CONSULTING SA	€ 90,000.00	1	€ 90,000.00
Grand Total	€ 1,108,045	4	€ 860,006

Top Academia

Higher Education	Total Cost	Signed Grants	EU Contribution
UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	€ 170,643.75	1	€ 170,643.75
UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	€ 127,625.00	1	€ 127,625.00
Grand Total	€ 298,269	2	€ 298,269

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Horizon Europe FCT Proposals Summary

Figure 7 presents a comparative overview of Portugal's and the EU's performance in **Horizon Europe FCT** proposal activities, allowing for a direct analysis of the Portuguese contribution and competitiveness.

Portugal's participation is characterised by a moderate volume of submitted proposals combined with a very high level of success. Portuguese organisations were involved in a total of 81 eligible proposals, representing a smaller share of overall submissions when compared to other leading countries, which recorded a significantly higher number of proposals.

Portugal	81	21	110	€ 20,338,506.98	26%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate
EU	278	39	4458	€ 1,099,171,410.00	14%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate

Figure 7: Statistics for Horizon Europe proposal submission for Portugal compared to the EU overall

A total of 21 proposals involving Portuguese participants were retained for funding, placing Portugal among the most successful countries in absolute terms relative to its size. This is further reflected in the total number of 110 eligible applications, indicating a focused but consistent level of engagement across the call topics.

Notably, Portugal achieves a success rate of 26%, making it the highest-performing country in terms of proposal success rate across the EU. This significantly exceeds both the EU average and the performance of comparable countries, highlighting the strong competitiveness and quality of Portuguese proposals.

Portugal presents a highly efficient and competitive participation profile, combining a relatively limited number of submissions with an exceptional success rate. This suggests strong alignment with call priorities and a targeted, high-quality approach to proposal preparation within the Portuguese **FCT** research community.

Horizon Europe FCT Projects Summary

The number of projects with strong Portuguese participation has increased, with Portugal consistently engaging as a relevant partner in a wide range of initiatives. Portuguese organisations are well integrated in **FCT** projects, frequently contributing to core technical tasks, pilot activities, and specialised work packages, particularly in areas such as digital investigation and data-driven security solutions.

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
GANNDALF	A Ground-breaking collaboration framework realizing the next era of cybercrime Detection And multi-stakeholder investigation For LEAs, judicial ecosystems, and citizens.	RIA	2
CLARUS	Building clarity and preventing bias in digital forensic examination, interorganisational communication and interaction	RIA	2
KOBAN	Identifying future capabilities for Community Policing	RIA	2
LAGO	LESSEN DATA ACCESS AND GOVERNANCE OBSTACLES	IA	2
NARCOSIS	Non-targeted forensic multidisciplinary platform for investigation of drug-related fatalities	IA	2
ForMAT	FORENSIC METHYLATION ANALYSIS TOOLSETS (FORMAT)	RIA	2
SALUS	Strengthening law enforcement with advanced IoT forensic tools and enriched investigation schemes, realised by a Software Defined Network Security-as-a-Service architecture	RIA	2
VANGUARD	advanced technological solutions coupled with societal-oriented Understanding and Awareness for Disrupting trafficking in human beings	IA	1
Ceasefire	Advanced versatile artificial intelligence technologies and interconnected cross-sectoral fully-operational national focal points for combating illicit firearms trafficking	IA	1
GATHERINGS	COMMON STANDARDS FOR SECURITY, PRIVACY AND COST OF THE SURVEILLANCE OF PUBLIC GATHERINGS	CSA	1
ENSEMBLE	Enhanced AI-based cybercrime-oriented collaborative investigation technologies and capabilities	RIA	1
EMERITUS	Environmental crimes' intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources	IA	1
FERMI	Fake News Risk Mitigator	IA	1

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
IMPROVE	Improving Access to Services for Victims of Domestic Violence by Accelerating Change in Frontline Responder Organisations	IA	1
SafeHorizon	Innovations in Detecting and Disrupting Crime-as-a-Service Operations	RIA	1
TENSOR	Reliable biometric Technologies to assist Police authorities in combating terrorism and organized crime	IA	1
OSPREY	Online Safety and Security for Protection of Public-Facing Professionals and Democratic Resilience	RIA	1
CapCell	Innovative forensic trace investigation via microfluidics and single-cell genomics	RIA	1
SALVUS	SALVUS (Ensuring Safer justice outcomes in online, including undercover, child sexual abuse investigations)	RIA	1
DETECTOR	Deepfake Evidence and Technology for Forensic Content Oversight and Research	RIA	1
BTL-COP	Building Trust and Leadership to challenge global homophobic crime in a police Community Of Practice (BTL-COP)	RIA	1

This level of engagement demonstrates Portugal's capacity to actively contribute to cross-border R&D activities and to position itself as a reliable and competitive partner within **Horizon Europe** projects, despite its smaller ecosystem.

The following section presents a series of charts detailing the policy, functional, and technological coverage of the projects, based on the comprehensive list of projects outlined above.

Figure 8: Policy project coverage according to projects with Portuguese participation

Figure 9: L3 Policy coverage according to projects with Portuguese participation

Figure 10: Functions coverage according to projects with Portuguese participation

Figure 11: Technology coverage according to projects with Portuguese participation

Final Remarks

Portugal's participation in the **FCT** research ecosystem under **Horizon Europe** demonstrates a competitive and well-positioned profile, characterised by strong proposal performance, consistent project involvement, and specialised expertise in key security domains. Despite operating within a smaller national ecosystem, Portuguese organisations have shown the ability to compete effectively with larger Member States, securing a significant number of projects and achieving the highest success rate in proposal evaluations.

From a policy perspective, Portugal shows a balanced coverage across all **FCT** domains, with a clear emphasis on **Cybercrime**, complemented by strong engagement in **Organised Crime**, particularly trafficking and economic crime, and relevant contributions to human and societal issues and **Terrorism and Radicalisation**. This distribution reflects both European priorities and national expertise, positioning Portugal as a contributor to a wide range of security challenges.

In terms of functional capabilities, Portuguese participation is strongly oriented towards **Investigation and Forensics**, supported by capabilities in **Data and Intelligence Management**, **Secure Communication**, and **Training Activities**. This functional profile highlights Portugal's role in supporting operational and intelligence-led approaches, particularly in areas requiring advanced analytical and investigative skills.

Technologically, Portugal demonstrates a clear focus on digital and data-driven solutions, with strengths in **Internet-based Investigation**, **Data Storage and Exchange** systems, **Digital Forensics**, and **Interoperable Communication Technologies**. This confirms a positioning aligned with the increasing digitalisation of security threats and the growing importance of information-centric approaches to **Law Enforcement**. At the same time, participation remains more concentrated among a limited number of actors, with relatively lower involvement from SMEs and private-sector entities. Expanding industrial participation and strengthening the role of SMEs represent a key opportunity for enhancing Portugal's impact and scaling its contribution within the European ecosystem.

Overall, Portugal represents a focused, competitive, and increasingly relevant actor within the **FCT** ecosystem, combining strong specialisation in digital security domains with broad engagement across policy areas, and demonstrating the capacity to deliver high-quality contributions within European collaborative research.

For more information and guidance regarding Portuguese participation in Horizon Europe Cluster 3 and potential collaboration opportunities, stakeholders are encouraged to consult the National Contact Points (NCPs) available through the Horizon Europe NCP Portal: <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/>, where dedicated Portuguese NCPs can provide support on funding opportunities, partner search, and proposal development.

A note on data sources

The data used to compile this report is from the following sources

- **ENACT Stakeholder Directory**, where relevant organisations participating in **Horizon Europe**, **Horizon 2020** or relevant security events have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- **ENACT Project Directory**, where relevant projects have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- The **Horizon Dashboard** for R&I Projects and R&I Proposals.⁵

An explorable version of the **ENACT Stakeholders Directory** is available on the **ENACT** website.⁶

⁵Horizon Dashboard - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

⁶ENACT Stakeholders Map - <https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

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